

Romanian Eurasianism? Mapping the political ideology of Călin Georgescu

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Abstract

This article investigates the meteoric and unexpected political rise of Călin Georgescu in Romanian domestic politics during the last two years by concentrating on his political philosophy, which is closely linked to the neo-Eurasianism developed by the Russian far-right intellectual Alexandr Dugin. Exploring philosophical, political, economic, and religious arguments, after a preliminary analysis of Eurasianism as historical, cultural, and ideological phenomenon, the article brings forward the concept of Romanian Eurasianism as it is embedded in Georgescu's political philosophy. The recent and sudden growth of this branch of Eurasianism can be considered odd, up to a certain point, since it does not rely on an important popular support for Russia in Romanian public opinion. Therefore, its main causes can be found within the tremendous social and economic rifts affecting contemporary Romania: Romanian Eurasianism is not the product of mischievous external influences as it is, first and foremost, a consequence of the improper domestic policies that have built up unprecedented levels of discontent within Romanian society, especially among its most disadvantaged members.

Keywords

ideology; political philosophy; Christian nationalism; multipolarism; inequality

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Introduction

In December 2024, the Constitutional Court of Romania suddenly annulled the first round of presidential elections, plunging the country into the deepest political turmoil since the anticommunist Revolution of 1989. The whole electoral process was compromised by Russian interference on social media, it was claimed, and this allowed for a relatively unknown candidate with extreme-right leanings, Călin Georgescu, to surpass more prominent political figures of the radical right, such as George Simion, the leader of the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR), and reach second position, just before Elena Lasconi, leader of the neoliberal party Save Romania Union (USR). Fueled by deep social and economic inequalities, and also by an overall popular resentment towards mainstream politics, Georgescu's chances of becoming president were considerable.

Beside allegations, no official proof of Russian implication in the presidential elections was delivered by Romanian authorities (Despa, 2025). However, Georgescu's fulminant electoral ascension, considering his position as an outsider of the Romanian political system and the modest scores he obtained at previous presidential elections, raised many questions. Although support for Russia among Romanians was below 6% in early 2025 (Popovici, 2025), it was still maintained that the political rise of Georgescu was an accident fueled by external factors and not by the deep discontent of lower social classes localized especially in the rural and semi-rural areas towards the political elite (Rogozanu, 2025). Although Russia's involvement in the political dynamics of Eastern European countries is very likely, given the context of the Ukraine war and the deterioration of the European Union – Russia relation, my paper also approaches Georgescu's electoral success as a domestic, rather than foreign political affair.

However, I deploy Georgescuist ideology as a new branch of Eurasianism, an eclectic Russian ideology that will be discussed in the next sections of the paper, although it is also influenced by local interwar right-wing ideologies (Marincea, 2025). Georgescuism was never analyzed before as a subspecies of Eurasianism. This ideological affiliation raises important questions, such as: what are philosophical, political, economic and religious similarities between Georgescuism and Eurasianism? Are there notable differences between the two parts? What are the implications of theorizing Georgescuism as a new form of Eurasianism? Which were the main domestic factors that allowed Georgescuist Eurasianism to become such an influent political ideology in such a short amount of time? How relevant were direct foreign political influences for this outcome?

Beside the literature review and methodology section, which further fleshes out the article in terms of theoretical and historical context, along with information regarding how the paper unfolds, the article pinpoints philosophical, political, economic, and religious implications that further consolidate the already strong affinities existing between Georgescuism and Eurasianism. The conclusions section endorses Georgescuism as a new type of Eurasian ideology.

Literature review and methodology

Drawing from the works of early Eurasianists like Nikolai Trubetzkoy (1991; see also Vinkovetski, Schlacks, 1996), or neo-Eurasianists like Alexandr Dugin (2017), and also from relevant scholars of Eurasianism like Marlène Laruelle (2008), Didier Chaudet, Florent Parmentier and Benoît Pelopidas (2009), Paolo Pizzolo (2020), Mark Bassin and Gonzalo Pozo (2017) or Dmitry Shlapentokh (2006), among others, this article emphasizes the many features of Eurasianism that are highly compatible with Georgescuism. It starts with the philosophical ones, grounded, as we are about to see, in the philosophy of Martin Heidegger, and then gradually advances towards political, economic, and religious issues. In this regard, the works of Georgescu himself prove to be an important resource

(Malița, Georgescu, 2010; Georgescu, 2012; Georgescu, 2016; Georgescu, 2023). Finally, in the conclusion section, and building on the gap existing in the already mentioned literature, the concept of Romanian Eurasianism is advanced.

The main hypothesis I work with is that even if Georgescu's political ideology can be considered a new form of Eurasianism, this does not indicate a growing influence of Russia within the Romanian political scene. On the contrary: as shown in the introduction, Russia is trusted nowadays by less than 6% of Romanians. This is because Georgescuist Eurasianism is a result of the deep cleavages affecting Romanian society: an outburst of popular revolt fueled by local unrest that contextually borrows the vocabulary of an eclectic and imperial ideology without neglecting Romanian undemocratic ideologies from the early 20th century as well. As Laruelle has argued, the expansion of Eurasianism after the end of the Soviet Union did not necessarily signal unity and strength across different cultures and nations, but a growth of peripheral currents of Eurasianism (Turkish, Iranian, Kazakh and so on) to the detriment of Russian versions (Laruelle, 2008: 204-208).

Building on the methodology of qualitative comparative politics, the article starts by investigating how Eurasianism and Georgescuism borrow consistently from Heidegger's philosophy of being, history and modernity. Furthermore, politics and international relations are brought into question in order to show how and why, drawing from unicity of each culture, Eurasianism and Georgescuism are both influenced by the political ideas of German romanticism of the 19th century and by a sense of exceptionalism that run deep through different versions of Romanian nationalism as well: the ultranationalism of the extreme right ideologies from the 1930s, the conservative nationalism from the second half of the 19th century, the national-communism from the 1960-1980 period and even the liberal nationalism that emerged after 1989 (Mihăilescu, 2017; for an interpretation of Eurasianism as exceptionalism, see Dughin, 2014). As forms of authoritarian populism that rely on a heavy metaphysics of land, people, and destiny, both Eurasianism and Georgescuism insist on a very truncated understanding of multipolarity, one that excludes liberal democracies, Sorosism, understood as a form of contemporary antisemitism, and modernity in general. However, as it will be argued throughout the article, Georgescuist Eurasianism is less sententious and more pragmatic in international problems than its Russian counterpart. It also lacks the imperial dimension of the latter, due to the size and political capacities of Romania as a small power on the global political stage.

Next, when it comes to economic matters, Eurasianism and Georgescuism deploy an anticapitalist rhetoric reminiscent of left ideologies. However, this shallow anticapitalism addresses only the effects, not the causes of structural inequalities present in modern societies. Furthermore, the solutions advanced by Eurasianism and Georgescuism in this matter rely on the debatable untainted capitalism of small, preferably rural entrepreneurs, against the neoliberal monopolies that prevent sustainable growth and meritocracy on a par with local traditions. Finally, religious aspects that support the claim of Georgescuism as a variation of Eurasianism are brought forward, with the aim of proving that the Orthodoxy that irrigates both is more ecumenical in the case of the latter and less so in the case of the former. As previously mentioned, the conclusion section proposes, on the basis of the overall argumentation, the concept of Romanian (or Georgescuist) Eurasianism.

Eurasian ideology: origins and development

Eurasianism developed the early 20th century, more precisely, immediately after the First World War, when a group of Russian conservative intellectuals were forced to emigrate from Bolshevik Russia into Western Europe. Displaced, deeply anti-communist, and willing to contribute to Russia's political future, the first Eurasianists had very diverse intellectual backgrounds (linguists, musicologists,

theologians and so on), but stood firmly against Europe and the 'Roman-German' culture in favor of the unicity of Russianness, understood as a historical and cultural blend between European and Asian features, a mixture in which the Asian dimension of Russian identity was presented as being more pronounced than the European one (Vinkovetski, Schlacks, 1996).

Early Eurasianists considered that instead of competing with the 'materialist' West, Russia should discover its authentic self as a bridge between Europe and Asia, bringing forward an organicist metaphysics that treasured Orthodox spirituality, political collectivism, imperial (but non-chauvinistic) nationalism and an organic state where procedural matters or the separation of powers were renounced in favor of a mystical union between the rulers and the ruled. 'Western parliamentarism' held no place in the Eurasianist political outlook. No one could search justice against the state; different opinions would be allowed on geographical and ethnic, not so much social bases, but the right to political decision was confined solely to a Eurasian elite which could not be contested. Only obeyed ('Author's introduction', 1996; Savitskii, 1996: 5-6; Laruelle, 2008: 28-31; Chamberlain, 2008: 247; Riasanovsky, 1996: 128-129). Instead of democracy, which was considered to weaken the political body, early Eurasianists proposed an ideocracy based on sacrifice and altruism (Trubetskoy, 1991: 269), a sort of organicist conservatism combined with a socialist paternalism that paid attention to the needs of the many without allowing them to become politically salient. Furthermore, they also criticized in harsh terms European colonialism, which is peculiar coming from a preponderantly right-wing movement, but becomes understandable if we take into account its unrepentant anti-Westernism and the attempt to fuel anti-European attitudes among the colonized peoples (Riasanovsky, 1996: 125-126; Trubetskoy, 1991: 54-55, 138-140; Bassin, Glebov, Laruelle, 2015: 9).

Although favoring authoritarianism, the first Eurasians were careful enough to dissociate themselves from rising fascism during the 1930s, despite some initial sympathies in this regard (Vinkovetski, 1996: 148-149; Trubetskoy, 1991: 286-287, 334). Like neo-Eurasianists, the pioneers of this new cultural ideology bemoaned the European influence that, starting with czar Peter the Great in the 18th century, was accused of pushing Russia away from its historical path. The Bolshevik revolution, guided by Marxism, another European ideology, was perceived as just another political event that continued this harmful trend. Even if these first Eurasianists insisted they possessed a modern worldview, they were deeply influenced by the German political romanticism from the 19th century, an anti-Enlightenment philosophy that cherished a rural way of life based on ethnic mysticism. The Slavophile movement from the previous century, opposed to the Westernizing trend, can be interpreted as a form of Russian romanticism that paved the way for Eurasianism, even if some Eurasianist condemned it for being too dogmatic (Laruelle, 2008: 20; Suvchinskii, 1996: 17, 21, 23; Berlin, 2008: 155-169; Trubetskoy, 1991: 206; Copilaş, 2009: 65-80).

As the Soviet Union grew stronger under Stalin, some Eurasianists became sympathetic towards the rise of Eurasia and believed that, with proper help, Stalinism could be transformed into a more nationalistic political system. While this happened due to various reasons and without Eurasianist input, several Eurasianist turned partially pro-Stalinist, while other retained their anti-Bolshevik convictions. Some Eurasians even went back to the Soviet Union in order to defend it from the invasion perpetrated by national-socialist Germany in 1941, but they were met with distrust by Soviet authorities and sent to prison or camps. Divided, weakened, and slipping into political irrelevance, the early Eurasianist movement gradually disappears after the Second World War (Paradowski, 2006: 108; Copilaş, 2009).

However, starting with the 1960s, and especially during the next two decades, Eurasianism is rediscovered by underground nationalist movements from the Soviet Union. The influential writings

of popular historian and anthropologist Lev Gumiliov are considered the link between classical Eurasianism and pro-Soviet Eurasianism, a form of nationalism tolerated, but officially unacknowledged by Soviet authorities. Only after the Soviet Union's disintegration in late 1991 can neo-Eurasianism truly emerge. Unlike classical Eurasianism, neo-Eurasianism is fond of right-wing extremism, more antisemitic, and also more geopolitically oriented. If classical Eurasianism can be considered a culturally defensive conservative movement, neo-Eurasianism is definitely embracing an imperial nationalism with clear fascist leanings, tailored on the popular discontent produced by post-Soviet economic and social crises and also by a sense of geopolitical downfall (Laruelle, 2008: 10; Rossman, 2006: 168, 173-174; Sheiko, Brown, 2017: 126; Trubetzkoy, 1991: 357; Copilaș, 2009).

Despite its diversity, neo-Eurasianism was gradually unified during the early 2000s around the writings and the personality of Alexandr Dugin, a former Russian nationalist that advocates for a 'conservative revolution', for a multipolar world freed from Western hegemony, and for tactical alliances with different radical right-wing movements all across Europe, Asia, and the rest of the world where anti-American positions are consolidated (Laruelle, 2015a). If classical Eurasianism resented the 'German-Roman' culture, namely Europe and its cosmopolitanism (Trubetzkoy, 1991: 4-6), neo-Eurasianism adapts to present day geopolitical realities and fosters, as previously mentioned, anti-Americanism. According to this perspective, the future of the world lies in the outcome of the conflict between land powers like Russia (tellurocracies), and sea powers like the United States (thalassocracies). Western material decadence is still despised by the new Eurasianist movement, which is also less open towards non-Christian religions and also its Asian legacy (Laruelle, 2015b: 188; Chaudet, Parmentier, Pelopidas, 2009). Therefore, one could claim, alongside Laruelle, that 'today's Eurasia is founded on a fundamental ambiguity—a nostalgia for empire and the fear of diversity' (Laruelle, 2015b: 192).

Deeply influenced by Alain de Benoist, the radical right-wing French intellectual that developed, decades ago, the ideology of Eurofascism, Dugin argues in favor of 'conservative revolutions' all around the globe, the fading of classical right-left political ideologies, tellurocracies and also against materialism and globalization (Dughin, 2017; Pizzolo, 2020: 92, 172-173; Rossman, 2006: 162; Benoist, 2016a; Benoist, 2016b; Benoist, 2017a; Benoist, 2017b; Benoist, 1998). Dugin and Benoist also share a deep commitment towards German romanticism and, especially the former, towards the German geopolitical school of the interwar period (Benoist, 1998: 69-76; Dugin, 2017; Dugin, 2011: 56). We will further explore Dugin's Eurasianism in the next section of the article, while pointing out its Heideggerian philosophical underpinnings that also fuel Georgescuist Eurasianism.

Heidegger reloaded: philosophical affinities between Eurasianism and Georgescuism

Dasein, technology, history: these are the three main Heideggerian concepts used by Dugin to reinforce classical Eurasianism, turning it into a 'conservative revolution' with a distinguishable fascist outlook and an anti-modern core that would have surely stirred some level of unrest among the first Eurasians. Dasein refers to a form of existence situated between the ontic, that is the actual, evenimential level of existence, and that of ontology, which investigates the historical development of being. The Dasein, individual and/or community in Heidegger's writings, but mostly the first, is the ontic always evaluated through an ontological prism. Since Antiquity, but especially during modern times, the Dasein lost its authenticity, its proper self, by posing itself separated from and superior to the surrounding phenomenological world: this duality marked the birth of metaphysics, and Heidegger is keen to expose it and alleviate its harmful influence upon the Dasein. Metaphysical thinking is converted, in modern times, into technocracy. Every modern political ideology, from liberalism to

socialism and fascism, all considered technologically driven economic growth as their main priority. But technology does not really solve our problems. It just deepens the alienation of the Dasein, its decadence, and the possibility of a meaningful reinvention through living up to the challenges of its own history. For Heidegger, history is not so much tradition, but destiny, the Dasein's capacity to seize the moment and become what it was meant to be all along, despite the temporary slumber in which modernity has thrown it into (Heidegger, 2008: 385-389; Heidegger, 1977: 3-35; Heidegger, 2001: 74-86).

Dugin, who wrote an entire book on the philosophy of Heidegger (Dugin, 2014), considers the Eurasian Dasein to be 'archeomodern', that is, only superficially modern. This technological modernity prevents the Eurasian Dasein from reaching full, archaic authenticity (Dugin, 2011). However, this is just a temporary obstacle on the historical path of the Dasein in fulfilling its ontological destiny (Dugin, 2017: 568). This is why the only modernity a Eurasian could accept is only technological, not moral (Dugin, 2017: 239-245). Since Eurasianism represents a quest for a true identity overshadowed by the West (Dugin, 2014: 253), accepting the cosmopolite, liberal modernity of the West would mean the end of Russia and its irreplaceable unicity.

Georgescu is also trying to bring forward a rural, Romanian identity that was depleted by almost two centuries of Western modernization, based on the rediscovery of popular 'geniuses' and the latent energies' of the people that kept traditions going despite a growing diffusion of inauthenticity (Malița, Georgescu, 2010: 22, 151-152, 157). In these challenging times, the Romanians must choose between growing into a proper nation or regressing back into a mere population (Georgescu, 2012: 19). In order to do so, Romania must rise to the 'heights of its great history' (Georgescu, 2012: 44). Critical of the Western materialism that has engulfed the country, cutting its access to its own history and thereby leaving it to ontologically 'wander' in inauthenticity (Georgescu, 2012: 197) - , Georgescu is, like Dugin, advocating as well for a type of technocracy, a managerial philosophy ('professionalization') that does not touch the main moral aspects of Romanian identity but, on the contrary, fosters 'national pride' (Georgescu, 2012: 50-56, 113). We will come back to the concept of professionalization latter.

In a stance reminding of national-communist protochronism, Georgescu argues that Romania created its own unique and treasurable civilization (Georgescu, 2016: 11). One that is threatened, nowadays, by the 'narcissistic and illusory technical thought' developed within the Western civilization (Georgescu, 2016: 21). 'Tehno-globalism' does away with ontology, with proper being, replacing it with frivolity, as 'living, unmediated bonds between people' are replaced by 'technical relations' (Hurduzeu, 2023: 19-26). 'We are not only the descendants of Rome, we are also the descendants of Decebal and Michael the Brave, of Stephen the Saint and of the Brâncoveanu martyrs' (Georgescu, 2016: 67). In other words, Romanian identity is not only of Western descent; it possesses a strong local lineage as well, which is more important than foreign influences. Precisely like in the case of Eurasianism. Especially young people should remember this, in order to become truly 'responsible'. 'History is unfortunately minimalized, its wires are simply cut, the connection with the heroes and martyrs of the nation is lost, without taking into account that each generation creates the history of the ones who will follow' (Georgescu, 2016: 94; see also Georgescu, 2023: 169).

Politics and international relations: authoritarian populism and multipolarity, key elements of Eurasianism and Georgescuism

Dugin's Eurasianism is intended as the official political guide of the Vladimir Putin regime. Of course, as a statesman, Putin's Eurasianism is mostly pragmatic, while Dugin's Eurasianism is more theoretic.

Still, Dugin considers that his political philosophy is followed, to a certain extent, in both Russia's foreign and domestic policy, despite Putin's occasional hesitance and his compromises with Western liberalism (Dughin, 2017: 144, 539-540).

By appealing to the people, an arbitrary discursive projection, instead of institutions, by favoring personal, not procedural power, and by also stressing Russia's timeless identity and how it is strengthened in its historical competition with the materialist and decadent West (Dughin, 2017) – Eurasianism places itself in the family of authoritarian populisms, although Dugin personally rejects the populist label (Laruelle, 2008: 127, 142). This is a right wing populism, similar to American neoconservatism, that lacks an anti-elitist position, typical for populist movements (most likely because it benefits from the support of the Putin regime) and, contrary to left-wing populisms that endorse social protest and political critique – projects the image of a powerful and charismatic leader able to defend Russian/Eurasian identity and, even more, guide it to geopolitical success against Western hegemony (Chaudet, Parmentier, Pelopidas, 2009; for an analysis of authoritarian populism, see Bugaric, 2019, and for a general typology of populism, Mișcoiu, 2012: 25-44). Georgescuist Eurasianism shares all these features as well, including a powerful dose of anti-elitism.

Just like the first Eurasians, Dugin is also influenced by German romanticism and its anti-modern outlook based on a mystic apprehension of land and ethnicity (Dughin, 2017, 207, 402). And following Heidegger, he too perceives both liberalism and socialism as different expressions of the technological grip that has engulfed the modern world (Dughin, 2017: 347-8). His anti-liberal, conservative revolution is critical towards individualism, the French Revolution, human rights, and democracy: Russia as metaphysical entity is way above these petty details that only divide and weaken its political body (Dughin, 2017: 219-220, 436, 512, 543, 556). Furthermore, by empowering minorities, especially sexual minorities that shaken traditional morality, democracy and pluralism are working against the cohesion of the people and its capacity to meet its historical destiny (Dughin, 2017: 556). As already mentioned, Dughin's Eurasianism is also antisemitic. Just like in the case of Georgescu, his antisemitism is centered upon the person of George Soros, the capitalist magnate that has helped spread the culture of liberalism in Russia and Eastern Europe after the fall of the socialist regimes (Dughin, 2017: 560; Carvalho and Dughin, 2016: 37; Grigorescu, Dinu, 2025).

Since classical political ideologies no longer matter, the political systems they inspired, like liberalism, socialism, and fascism, are also outdated. Instead, Dugin proposes the fourth political theory, inspired as well by Heidegger (Dughin, 2014: 43; Sakwa, 2017: 213). Nothing more than 'revolutionary conservatism', Eurasianism is this fourth political theory (Dughin, 2011: 63; Carvalho and Dughin, 2016: 245), one that embraces both right-wing authoritarian populism and a form of socialist paternalism expressed through a shallow anticapitalism that will be analyzed in the next section of the article, and also the idea of a 'hedgehog state', rough with the foreign enemies of Russia/Eurasia, and gentle with its peoples (Dughin, 2017: 104, 205, 405). Through 'erotic patriotism', the Eurasian peoples will follow their natural instincts in order to procreate and to turn love into demographic expansion (Dughin, 2017: 202). This will consolidate the Eurasian geopolitical space, allowing it to boost its alliances with other civilizations from Asia, Africa, the Middle East and Latin America, and also with 'patriotic' movements from the West, in order to end the hegemony of American thalassocracy with its nomadic and entrepreneurial ethos – in favor of a truly multipolar world, one in which Eurasia will regain once again its rightful place (Dughin, 2017: 257-380). After all, Dugin, precisely like Putin, holds the former Soviet Union to a high degree of esteem, with the exception of the Gorbachev period, when Western liberalism crept in, contributing to the subordination of Eurasia to the West (Dughin, 2011: 68).

Georgescuist Eurasianism is also authoritarian and, since it is lacking mainstream political support, highly anti-elitist. Its anti-elitism is codified as a harsh critique of ‘politicianism’, a derogatory concept used in Romania since late 19th century (Georgescu, 2012: 115, 178; Georgescu, 2016: 44). The post-communist social, economic and political crisis was partially diminished by Romania’s accession into the European Union in 2007 was entirely the consequence of catastrophic political management. Romania had experienced difficult periods in the 20th century (1916-1918, 1929-1933, 1940-1960), but they were all the result of war, economic crises or foreign occupation, Georgescu argues (Georgescu, 2012, 190-191).

While he considers Nicolae Ceaușescu a ‘semi-illiterate tyrant’, Georgescu acknowledges his contribution to the social and economic development of Romania during the 1960s and his decision to pay the country’s foreign debt entirely in the 1980s, even with the cost of a tremendous austerity that fueled the 1989 revolution. By paying back as soon as possible Romania’s debt to international financial organizations like the International Monetary Fund or the World Bank, Ceaușescu ‘avoided humiliating interest rates’ and ‘did not add another layer to the fat of international extortioners’ (Malița, Georgescu, 2010: 182-183; Georgescu, 2023: 120-121). It is noticeable that Georgescu rejects only the first, ‘internationalist’ period of the former communist regime, when the country was still fully dominated by Moscow. This is consistent with Dugin’s favorable approach to national-communism, including Stalinism, and his already invoked rejection of glasnost and perestroika developed in the Gorbachev era under the ideological influence of the West (Dughin, 2017: 79-82).

Like in the case of Dugin, Georgescu’s political philosophy is built with the help of a ‘powerful and healthy’ state, one that works in favor of the people, not against them (Georgescu, 2012: 46). Curiously enough, this state should be de-centralized as much as possible, but still remain powerful and socially involved (Georgescu, 2016: 42). Contrary to the imperial nationalism professed by Russian Eurasianism (Chaudet, Parmentier, Pelopidas, 2009), Georgescu favors a ‘Christian’, ‘non-expansive’, non-xenophobic and non-racist nationalism (Georgescu, 2016: 65-66, 105), one that suits better Romania’s more modest geopolitical ambitions. Furthermore, this powerful state working in favor of people, not politicians, should be conceived around the ‘national interest’, which Georgescu places above political parties, political doctrines and electoral stakes (Georgescu, 2012: 39, 59; Georgescu, 2016: 77). Above negotiations, and, in other words, above democracy. Political parties are compared with organized criminal groups that have led Romania astray (Georgescu, 2016: 61). If ‘old’ political parties cannot be radically reformed in order to work for the benefit of the people, and not for their ‘primitive’ interests alone, they should be abolished altogether (Georgescu, 2023: 184). ‘Romania will thrive again when the country will be ruled by people of the land (oamenii gliei, m.n.), who will make history, not politics. And those times are near’ (Georgescu, 2016: 36). These natural leaders are not elected but imposed by their sheer personal ‘virtues’ (Georgescu, 2016: 37) and validated by the ‘wisdom of the people’ (Georgescu, 2012: 199). Until this happens, the country’s political regime will remain a ‘demonocracy’, not a proper democracy (Georgescu, 2016: 85).

Georgescu loathes sexual minorities, abortions and multiculturalism; promoting them amounts to ‘leftism’ in general, although not ‘neo-Marxism’, which is nothing but another facet of neoliberalism, through which Georgescu understands contemporary Western capitalism based on globalization, cultural dominance and extractivism, leaving behind nothing but depleted areas and humiliated peoples (Georgescu, 2016: 63; Georgescu, 2023: 31-33, 191). Still, as mentioned above, Georgescu is strongly in favor of minimal, neoliberal states. Instead of Western ideologies, Romania should look back to its true heroes, like mothers, martyrs, or ‘saints’ from communist prisons (many of them belonging to the former fascist Iron Guard, like Ion Gavrilă Ogoranu), to historical figures like

Michael the Brave, Tudor Vladimirescu and Alexandru Ioan Cuza, or authoritarian right-wing military dictators like marshal Antonescu (Georgescu, 2016: 63; Georgescu, 2023: 188).

In the same vein as Dugin, and Heidegger, before him, Georgescu reduces both neoliberalism and the former Romanian communist dictatorship to symptoms of modernity traceable to the Jacobinism that emerged with the French Revolution and promoted materialism, atheism, universalism, progress, and development. This harmful 'social engineering' destroys 'natural capital' and turns people into individual commodities, making them renounce their traditions and national origins (Georgescu, 2016: 38; Georgescu, 2023: 192).

As for international relations, 'Romania must affirm its vocation as bridge and as space of dialogue and complementarity between cultures and must capitalize the advantages coming from its privileged geographic position on the future routes of commercial and energy exchanges between the East and the West of the Eurasian space' (Georgescu, 2016: 184; see also Georgescu, 2023: 51, 120). Non-Western multipolarity at its peak. As a minor Eurasian power, Romania must relearn to develop friendly relations with all its neighboring countries and expand on its geographic position. Normalizing the relations with Russia thus becomes a priority, especially since Georgescu considers Putin a 'patriot', although he allowed Russian economy to become entangled with 'globalism', that is, neoliberal capitalism (Georgescu, 2016: 159-163; Georgescu, 2023: 160). After all, Dugin himself is a great admirer of historians of religion and philosophers like Mircea Eliade and Lucian Blaga. Romania is thus compelled to choose between euro-atlanticism and euro-continentalism, between the 'asphaltic' American civilization that has become dominant worldwide with the help of globalization, but where, in the absence of roots, nothing really grows, and between the project of the Greater Eastern Europe, where it could truly fulfill its historical and geopolitical destiny (Dughin, 2011: 13-18; Raețchi, 2017: 86-87; Dughin, 2017: 368-369, 487).

Anticapitalism? Eurasian and Georgescuist economics

When it comes to economy, both Dugin and Georgescu profess certain anticapitalistic attitudes; however, these are directed only against the Western, foreign capitalistic monopolies, and never against the smaller, national capital that is forced to compete in unjust conditions with foreign investments (at least in Romania). Unlike Dugin, which is not so specific in economic matters, Georgescu is, although always within the theoretical framework laid down previously by his ideological 'mentor'.

Dugin's understanding of economy starts with the economic nationalism developed in the 19th century by Friedrich List, although he also touches upon Joseph Schumpeter or John Maynard Keynes. Protectionism, the growth of national capital and the securing of Russia's position within the global economy, these are the main coordinates of Dugin's economic vision (Dughin, 2017: 432-433). Furthermore, Dugin envisages a rural Eurasian economy, on in which cities will no longer occupy the most important position, and the most important industries will be shifted to the countryside. The motive? Cities and urbanization pave the way for globalist and cosmopolite ideologies that threaten the Eurasian ideological project (Dughin, 2017: 456-457; see also Pizzolo, 2020: 248). Georgescu will assume and elaborate on this rural economy further.

Balancing between right and left, Eurasianists do not employ a definitive economic model in their quest for geopolitical supremacy. Each Eurasian people should develop according to its own tradition and unique identity. Some important economic sectors should be controlled directly by the state and not left to the unpredictable and pretentious free market, while others should become the responsibility of local, national capital, thus allowing the primacy of a supervised market development.

Each 'Great Space' should create a self-centered but not necessarily autarchic economy, one that is deeply interconnected and prospers mainly on the basis of its own resources (Pizzolo, 2020: 249).

Let us see now how these tenets of Eurasian economics are elaborated upon by Georgescu. It is worth mentioning that the anti-Western tone of Georgescu was amplified only during the last decade; his first books endorsed the EU as the main chance of economic development for Romania and also bemoaned the 'medieval mentalities, growing illiteracy, the return to mysticism as a mass phenomenon, the nostalgia for dictatorship, the waiting for a providential savior' and also the 'social and cultural apathy of the population' (Georgescu, 2012: 15; see also Georgescu, 2016: 45). It is definitely ironic how these shortcomings have contributed to his recent meteoric political rise to such a great extent. However, in his last book, Georgescu argues that Romania will respect its international alliances only to the extent its partners will do so, and that the EU and NATO have lost their moral and political compass (Georgescu, 2023: 119, 237-238).

Critical of both neoliberalism and socialism as atheist political regimes based upon foreign ideologies, Georgescu favors a Christian nationalism that would help rebuild the country by re-professionalizing it. This means massive investment in young families, demographic growth, in small, local business, and also in sports and healthy alimentation. Like Dugin, Georgescu deeply intertwines the social and economic growth of Romania with small business developed by rural entrepreneurs, away from the cities that fostered cosmopolite ideologies and a decline of national identity and traditions. However, he also recognizes the potential of information technology for the future of the country, thus allowing a certain economic role for cities in his economic project. Critical of extractivist capitalism and its contribution to both the ongoing climate crisis and also to the ruthless exploitation of national resources in poor and developing countries, Georgescu intends to use European funds and whatever help he can get in order to protect Romania's natural resources and use them for national growth, not for the benefit of foreign multinational corporations. He is also critical towards the underfinancing of education, which should be turned into a nationalist project, and the overwhelming bureaucracy that paralyzes local entrepreneurial initiatives. Like Dugin, Georgescu is paradoxically endorsing a strong national state while simultaneously complaining about the oversized Romanian state and arguing, in pure neoliberal fashion, for a minimal one and for lower taxes. An industry based solely and consumption and entertainment should be turned, once again, into a productive one. The example of interwar Romania, a presumably rural entrepreneurial nation, is eloquent for Georgescu, highlighting both his closeness towards radical right-wing nationalism and also towards social and economic discipline (Malița, Georgescu, 2010; Georgescu, 2012; Georgescu, 2016; Georgescu, 2023).

Taking all these into account, the need for a 'civic economy' that would dismantle the massification produced by capitalist consumerism is greater than ever. A civic economy would disrupt the growth cycles followed by crises that represent the mark of neoliberal capitalism, would foster national interest and would replace the empty individualism of a consumerist society with 'Christian personalism' (Georgescu, 2016: 118). Only when a civic economy is implemented, with the help of a national technocracy managed by an enlightened leader, only then Romania will become truly sovereign and rediscover its roots and its spirituality that created a wholesome civilization in the past (Georgescu, 2023: 209). The trope of Romania as civilization is reminiscent of national-communist protochronism, but the small-scale rural capitalism fiercely defended by Georgescu is definitely not compatible the centralized socialist economy. This is why Georgescuist economics is, considering the overall Georgescuist ideology, of a radical right-wing, not left-wing inspiration.

It follows that Georgescu's Christian nationalism is influenced first of all not necessarily by the fascist nationalism of the former Legionary movement, like it was argued (Marincea, 2025), but by the

economic program of the interwar peasant party, which turned progressively towards the radical right during the 1930s and until the postwar period, when political pluralism was abolished by the local communist party which instituted the republic in 1948. This program also argued for authority and Christian democracy, for anticommunism and for a small peasant capitalism that would propel grassroots meritocracy and contribute to the spiritual rebirth of the nation, unlike the liberal monopolies of the 1920s (see Niculae, Ilincioiu, Neagoe, 1994: 237-238, 254-255). However, given the fact that the EU is confronted for decades by the issue of agricultural overproduction, while Russia and China generally meet their alimentary demands from domestic sources, it is not clear where the output of such a rural industry envisaged by Georgescu would be channeled.

To conclude, there is no question that the anti-Westernism of both Russian and Georgescuist Eurasianism simulates anticapitalism but is not truly anticapitalistic. It just supports local, national capitalism at the expense of foreign, multinational corporations. Even when it laments the social and cultural effects produced by Western capitalist consumerism upon the natural resources, structural inequalities, and the spiritual wander of the youth from poor and developing countries. At best, it can be considered a shallow and incomplete anticapitalism, one that considers only the effects, but not the deep causes of this overreaching political economy.

Balancing between orthodoxy and ecumenism: religious implications of Eurasianism and Georgescuism

Early Eurasianists were more religiously tolerant than contemporary ones. Dugin, for example, allows only an instrumental role for Islam in the spiritual economy of neo-Eurasianism, considering it a 'tactical ally', therefore a disposable one, when the time will come (Dughin, 2017: 538; Laruelle, 2015b: 188). Even if Orthodoxy remains the main ingredient of Eurasian spirituality, each religious tradition should be cherished and protected, as long as it is not sectarian and/or extremist (Pizzolo, 2020: 250). Protestantism, historically responsible for the consolidation of liberal-bourgeois mentalities and of individualism in the West, is also disavowed (see Benoist, 2017a: 43; Trubetskoi, 1996: 88).

As for Georgescu, his Orthodoxy leaves no room for other religions. Georgescuist Eurasianism is spiritually less diverse than its Russian counterpart, but it compensates with a more political outlook. As already argued, it cherishes the traditional family and goes against sexual minorities. Moreover, in order to truly build the Christian nationalism that Georgescu is so fond of, one should not confound faith with 'magic'. Our deepest fears and anxieties presumably come from the abandonment of true faith; in order to regain it, one must 'work tirelessly' and even 'sacrifice' himself for the greater national good. Despite all these setbacks, 'profound Romania (still) exists, and the tidal river of ancestral faith flows quietly', bringing along 'hope and persistence in the fight for defending the motherland' (Georgescu, 2016: 58-59). But, until the moment of national rebirth gains momentum, 'in our country people literally die of hunger, the elderly are humiliated, the children have no future, the land is sold to foreigners, and our ancestral belief is made a mockery of' (Georgescu, 2016: 50).

Conclusion: the emergence of Romanian Eurasianism

This article deployed the political ideology of Georgescu in strong connection with the version of Eurasianism theorized by Dugin. After a brief analysis of Eurasianism in mostly historical and ideological terms, it brought to the forefront remarkable similarities between the two parts starting with philosophical affinities, going through political and economic shared perspectives and ending up with religious connections. Taking all these into account, it can be argued that Georgescuism should be considered a new form of Eurasianism. After a Russian, a Turkish, an Iranian, a Kazakh, a German, a

Japanese, a Hungarian, an Italian, a French and a Greek version of Eurasianism (Laruelle, 2015a; Bassin, Pozo, 2017; Bassin, Glebov, Laruelle, 2015), we are witnessing the emergence of a Romanian branch. This is definitely not something to brag about, unfortunately.

Furthermore, it is quite a paradoxical outcome, since, as already mentioned in the introductory section, Russia's influence in Romania is at a historical low. It follows that this radical right-wing ideology, this 'conservative revolution' with Romanian features is a product of profound social and economic inequalities produced after the 1989 Revolution, inequalities that are visible especially when comparing the rural and urban areas. This deep popular discontent fueled the rise of various radical right-wing parties during the previous years and, among them, the political ideology of Georgescu – one that borrows a foreign ideological vocabulary, that of Eurasianism, and cunningly adapts it to the social, political, economic and religious context of Romania.

Following the tradition of exceptionalism that affected all modern Romanian political ideologies, both democratic and undemocratic (Mihăilescu, 2017), Romanian Eurasianism proposes, in this vein, a new form of exceptionalism, one that borrows massively from the radical right-wing ideologies from the interwar period and, unlike them, is not anti-Russian, although it can neither be said that is Russophile. Even if Romanian communism was a Soviet product during the interwar period, it gradually developed, especially starting with the early 1960s, into a form of left-wing nationalism that turned progressively anti-Soviet. Historically, Romania's traditional hostility towards Russia endures, despite the recent electoral success of Romanian Eurasianism which is, once again, a development of the failures of postcommunist capitalism more than a devious foreign ideological import.

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